

The Complexity of Polydrug Abuse: Addressing the Growing Concern of Xylazine and Fentanyl Co-Use in India

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ABSTRACT

Background: The co-abuse of xylazine and fentanyl is a rising threat to human health, with xylazine, a veterinary tranquilizer, being added to opioids and other drugs in the illicit market. This combination leads to increased risks of overdose and severe adverse effects. Polydrug use, involving the simultaneous consumption of multiple drugs, including illegal substances and prescription medications, exacerbates the dangers associated with drug misuse.

Main Body: Xylazine and fentanyl co-abuse affect the central nervous and respiratory systems, resulting in profound respiratory depression and bradycardia. The combination's synergistic effects intensify sedation and pose significant risks in cases of overdose. The prevalence of xylazine as an adulterant in the illicit opioid supply has led to an alarming increase in opioid overdose deaths in several US states. In India, while there are no reported cases of xylazine and fentanyl co-abuse, the prevalence of opioid use remains a significant public health concern.

Management strategies for xylazine and fentanyl overdose involve emergency care measures, respiratory support, and blood pressure stabilization. Long-term recovery and withdrawal management present challenges due to limited information on chronic xylazine use. Psychosocial interventions and support services play a crucial role in the overall recovery process.

Conclusion: The co-abuse of xylazine and fentanyl necessitates immediate attention, and preventive measures are crucial to combat this global concern. Increased awareness, research, and evidence-based interventions are essential to address the complexities of polydrug use and promote a safer and healthier society. In India, initiatives like the *Nasha Mukta Bharat Abhiyaan* aim to address drug abuse and foster youth engagement to combat the issue. By understanding the risks and consequences of polydrug co-abuse, we can develop effective strategies to mitigate harm and safeguard the well-being of those affected.

Keywords Xylazine, Fentanyl, Polydrug, Opioids, Toxicity

BACKGROUND

Increasing use of Xylazine with Fentanyl a dangerous combination, is a seriously rising threat to human health. Xylazine, a veterinary tranquilizer also known as “Tranq”, “Tranq-dope”, “Sleep cut” a powerful sedative, Non-narcotic, Non-opioid has been approved by the Food and Drug Administration in 1972 for the sedative, analgesic and muscle relaxant for animals and it is often administered concomitantly with ketamine or barbiturates, Initially it was studied in humans as an antihypertensive but discontinued for the human use because of its adverse effects such as sedation, bradycardia, and hypotension.¹

It was found that it is more prevalent additive in the street drugs and spreading faster at an alarming rate. Opioids are a class of drugs derived from the opium poppy plant. They can be either naturally occurring or chemically synthesized, with substances like fentanyl being created in laboratories to mimic the chemical structure of the plant-based opioids.² Xylazine is most commonly added to these opioids and individuals who already have exposure to cocaine to be exposed to xylazine, and it is frequently added to illicit substances as an adulterant.^{3,4} Xylazine affects the central nervous system and facilitates respiratory depression, leading to increased risk of overdose. It slows a person’s breathing and heart rate and lowers their blood

pressure. An overdose can put them into a coma-like state, leaving them frozen and vulnerable for hours on the street.⁵

The dangerous additive effects of xylazine on drug addiction. While no specific drug has been approved for reversing xylazine's effects, the opioid antagonist naloxone has been used to mitigate the opioid effects of xylazine combined with fentanyl. Xylazine is associated with severe adverse effects, including the development of non-healing, debilitating wounds. The precise mechanism behind this phenomenon remains unclear, but it is suggested that xylazine may impede blood circulation, impairing the skin's healing abilities. Even minor skin issues such as pimples or needle punctures can progress into extensive, deep ulcers reaching the bone.⁵ Due to lack of knowledge about this adjuvant's presence can have dangerous complications especially if they are using for the first time.⁶

The accessibility and appeal of Xylazine in the illicit drug market. Xylazine can be easily obtained online without veterinary associations or legitimate justifications, especially from Chinese suppliers at low prices. Its affordability makes it an attractive adulterant for drug traffickers, allowing them to reduce the amount of fentanyl or heroin in mixtures for increased profits. Xylazine's longer-lasting effects compared to fentanyl attract users seeking prolonged experiences.

The presence of xylazine as an adulterant often goes unnoticed during seizures, and its blending with other drugs occurs at retail locations such as stash houses. However, the frequency of such occurrences remains uncertain. Subsequent forensic testing is necessary to identify xylazine in the illicit drug supply.⁷

Poly drug use

Polydrug use involves the recreational consumption of multiple drugs, including illegal substances and legally obtained medications. For instance, individuals may misuse cocaine while concurrently using alcohol and prescription sedatives or anti-anxiety drugs.⁸ Poly drug use aims to enhance desired effects, but combining central nervous system depressants like opioids and benzodiazepines can result in excessive sedation.

This practice is linked to addiction, depression, and behavioural problems, especially in adolescents. Withdrawal from poly drug use poses additional challenges. Understanding these dynamics is crucial for effective intervention and treatment strategies.⁹ The risk factors associated with drug misuse, specifically poly drug use. Factors such as minority status, community stress, family history of substance abuse, family environment, and early risk factors contribute to drug misuse.

Additionally, addictive drug prescriptions, mental illness, life stressors, and behavioral issues are identified as significant risk factors for poly drug use. Understanding these factors is crucial for developing effective prevention and intervention strategies. The addictive nature of substances brings about profound changes in the brain's motivational system, altering the processing of pleasure and reward. Over time, individuals become dependent on substances to experience pleasure and attain a sense of normalcy.⁸

This review aims to comprehensively analyse the combined effects of Xylazine and Fentanyl on the central nervous system, focusing on the associated toxicity and risks, particularly in cases of overdose.

By examining the underlying mechanisms contributing to heightened toxicity and exploring clinical manifestations, medical emergencies, and potential complications, the review seeks to enhance the understanding of healthcare professionals, policymakers, and researchers regarding poly drug abuse involving Xylazine and Fentanyl.

The ultimate objective is to inform the development of evidence-based prevention programs, harm reduction strategies, and policies targeted at addressing the escalating issue of poly drug abuse in India.

PREVALANCE

According to The State unintentional drug overdose reporting system [SUDROS], Xylazine in illicit drug mixtures exacerbating the opioid overdose crisis and resulting in opioid overdose deaths in numerous states and cities of United states, including Vermont, Maine, Massachusetts, Connecticut, Maryland, Pennsylvania [Specifically Philadelphia] and New York. In a recent study by Friedman and colleagues (2022), they discovered that Xylazine was present in ten jurisdictions across all four U.S. census regions.

Among these locations, Philadelphia had the highest prevalence of Xylazine-related deaths (25.8%), followed by Maryland (19.3%) and Connecticut (10.2%).¹⁰

Numerous governmental organizations at the national and state levels, such as the Drug Enforcement Administration (DEA), Food and Drug Administration (FDA), Centres for Disease Control and Prevention (CDC), and state public health departments, have issued alerts regarding the prevalence of Xylazine and its significant role in opioid overdose fatalities.

While Xylazine remains legally available in the United States, the FDA has implemented measures as of February 28, 2023, to impede its illicit usage and entry into the domestic market.

At present there are no reported cases of Xylazine with fentanyl co-abuse cases in India. The prevalence of opioid use in India highlights the significant public health concern, with heroin being the most commonly used opioid (1.14%), closely followed by pharmaceutical opioids (0.96%) and opium (0.52%).

It is particularly alarming that Sikkim, Arunachal Pradesh, Nagaland, Manipur, and Mizoram have emerged as regions with the highest prevalence of opioid use among the general population, exceeding 10%.¹¹

This review article aims to shed light on the magnitude of opioid use in India and underscore its importance as a pressing issue that requires immediate attention and comprehensive interventions.

PARAMETERS	<i>XYLAZINE</i>	<i>FENTANYL</i>
Molecular formula	C ₁₂ H ₁₆ N ₂ S	C ₂₂ H ₂₈ N ₂ O
Molecular weight	220.34 g/mol.	336.471 g/mol
Class	Strong synthetic alpha 2-adreno receptor agonist	Analgesic; Opioid
CAS number	7361-61-7	437-38-7
IUPAC name	N-(2,6-dimethylphenyl)-5,6-dihydro-4H-1,3-thiazin-2-amine	N-(1-(2-phenethyl)-4-piperidinyl)-N-phenyl-propanamide.
Brand names	Rompun, Anased, Sedazine, Chanazine	Sublimaze, Actiq, Durogesic, Effentora.
Route of administration	Inhalation, or injection (intravenous, intramuscular, or subcutaneous)	Sublingual, Transdermal
Dosage forms and strength	Intravenously–0.5 mL/100 lbs body weight (0.5 mg/lb) Intramuscularly–1.0 mL/100 lbs body weight (1.0 mg/lb)	Transdermal system: 12 mcg/hour, 25 mcg/hour, 37.5 mcg/hour, 50 mcg/hour, 75 mcg/hour, 100 mcg/hour.
Chemical structure		

Abbreviations: CAS- Chemical Abstract services, IUPAC- International Union of Pure and Applied Chemistry^{12,13}

MECHANISM OF XYLAZINE IN ANIMALS AND HUMANS

Xylazine, a thiazine derivative as an alpha-2 adrenergic receptor agonist, has demonstrated a decrease in the release of norepinephrine and dopamine within the central nervous system, as observed in animal studies.¹⁴

Its sedative and analgesic effects are attributed to central nervous system depression, while its muscle relaxant activity is based on inhibiting intraneural impulse transmission. In horses, the pharmacological effects manifest within 10 to 15 minutes after intramuscular injection and 3 to 5 minutes following intravenous administration. The duration of the sleep like state, depth, and analgesia vary with dosage, typically lasting 1 to 2 hours and 15 to 30 minutes, respectively.

Xylazine reduces respiratory rate and can temporarily affect cardiac conductivity, resulting in a partial atrioventricular block. However, this is similar to what is observed in normal horses. Intravenous administration causes a transient increase followed by a slight decrease in blood pressure. Xylazine does not impact blood clotting time or other hematologic parameters.¹³

Cell studies conducted by both Wistar rat and PC12 shows that, xylazine administration was found to have an impact on adenosine triphosphate (ATP)ase and cyclic adenosine monophosphate (cAMP) levels. It also exhibited regulatory effects on the expression of GluR1, ERK, PKA, cAMP-response element binding protein (CREB), and brain-derived neurotrophic factor (BDNF) within the nervous system. However, no significant influence on GluR2 and protein kinase C (PKC) expression was observed. These findings suggest that xylazine may induce sedation and analgesia by modulating the PKA/ERK/CREB signaling pathway.¹⁵

Xylazine activates central presynaptic α_2 receptors in humans, leading to sedation, muscle relaxation, and analgesia. By partially blocking synapses in the central nervous system, it induces muscle relaxation. Xylazine enhances the effects of tranquilizers, sedatives, cataleptics, dissociative anaesthetics, and anaesthetic agents.

While it provides potent visceral analgesia, its analgesic effects in the extremities are minimal. Xylazine significantly affects the cardiovascular system by modulating the autonomic nervous system. Intravenous administration initially raises arterial blood pressure and myocardial contractility, followed by sustained hypotension and reduced myocardial contractility. Bradycardia and second-degree atrioventricular block commonly occur, but they can be reversed with a parasympatholytic like atropine.¹⁶

Mechanism of Fentanyl:

Fentanyl, with its potency 50 to 100 times greater than morphine, is primarily used in cancer pain management and post-operative pain relief. Its mechanism of action involves the activation of mu-opioid receptors,^{2,17} which are distributed in various regions of the brain, spinal cord, and other tissues. Fentanyl predominantly interacts with the mu-receptor, but it also binds to kappa and delta receptors, which are other types of opioid receptors.¹⁷

Mechanism of Xylazine-Fentanyl

Fentanyl primarily depresses the respiratory system, causing a slowdown in breathing that may lead to unconsciousness. Xylazine, on the other hand, primarily affects the nervous system, resulting in slowed breathing, heart rate, and decreased blood pressure. An overdose of these substances can induce a state resembling a coma, rendering individuals motionless and susceptible to harm for extended periods while on the streets.⁵

Xylazine can be consumed through various routes, including oral ingestion, smoking, snorting, and injection (intramuscular, subcutaneous, or intravenous). Compared to fentanyl, xylazine has a longer duration of effect. The inclusion of xylazine as an adulterant in fentanyl likely intensifies the euphoria and analgesia produced by fentanyl, leading to decreased injection frequency.³

The presence of xylazine alongside fentanyl or heroin appears to interfere with the brain's natural response to counteract rapid oxygen loss following opioid drug exposure. When administered individually, fentanyl or heroin induced a rapid and significant decrease in brain oxygen levels due to slowed breathing, followed by a gradual and prolonged increase. In contrast, the inclusion of xylazine resulted in more modest and sustained decreases in brain oxygen levels.⁷

SYNERGISTIC EFFECTS OF XYLAZINE AND FENTANYL

Evidence suggests that the co-administration of xylazine and fentanyl in humans can enhance the sedative effects and exacerbate the adverse effects of respiratory depression, bradycardia, and hypotension associated with fentanyl alone. This phenomenon is similar to the synergistic effects observed when benzodiazepines are combined with heroin or fentanyl.¹⁸ When xylazine is combined with fentanyl or other synthetic opioids, there is an increased risk of fatal overdoses due to the amplification of pharmacological effects, which further compromises respiratory function already affected by opioids.⁷

Interactions with the Central nervous system and respiratory system.

A Study Series conducted by NIDA Intramural Research Program with rat experiments to investigate the effects of xylazine when used as an adulterant with fentanyl and heroin.

investigated the effects of xylazine as an adulterant to fentanyl and heroin. In the first phase, researchers administered xylazine alone at different doses and observed sedation, muscle relaxation, decreased body temperature, and a dose-dependent decrease in brain oxygen levels.

In the second phase, fentanyl or heroin was administered alone, resulting in an initial rapid decrease in brain oxygen levels followed by a slower increase. However, when combined with xylazine, the rebound increase in brain oxygen was suppressed, leading to sustained lower levels compared to fentanyl or heroin alone. The xylazine-heroin mixture showed a particularly stronger and more prolonged initial decrease in brain oxygen compared to heroin alone.¹⁹

HEALTH CONSEQUENCES

Long term effects of Xylazine and Fentanyl co-abuse and its risk of dependence and addiction:

Limited information exists regarding the long-term effects of co-abusing xylazine and fentanyl. However, chronic fentanyl use can lead to physical dependence, addiction, and tolerance, requiring higher doses for the desired effect. Prolonged opioid use adversely affects the respiratory, gastrointestinal, immune systems, and cognitive function. Notably, the use of illicit drugs, including those contaminated with xylazine, carries unpredictable and potentially harmful consequences.^{20,21}

Physical health consequences

Xylazine exposure can result in dependence, addiction, and withdrawal symptoms characterized by agitation, vision changes, debilitating migraines, and severe anxiety upon dose reduction or cessation. These adverse effects can perpetuate substance abuse and hinder the management of opioid use disorder (OUD).²²

Xylazine, a potent animal sedative, is frequently combined with illicit fentanyl. Regardless of the route of administration, xylazine can inflict lasting harm on the body, often resulting in the development of significant skin ulcers, soft-tissue wounds, and necrosis, leading to premature skin death.²³ It exhibits synergistic toxic effects with opioids, heightening the potential for mental status depression and compromised airway function.²²

Mental health implications

Xylazine synergistically enhances the toxic effects of opioids, elevating the risk of mental status depression and compromised airway function.²⁴ It can potentiate the depressant effects of substances like fentanyl and heroin. Although xylazine alone does not induce the same level of respiratory depression as opioids, its profound impact on mental status can potentially result in airway compromise and subsequent suffocation.²⁵

CLINICAL PRESENTATION

Typical signs and symptoms of Xylazine and fentanyl co-abuse

Xylazine produces pharmacological effects in humans that are comparable to those of heroin, including bradycardia, hypotension, central nervous system depression, and respiratory depression. Xylazine overdose clinically resembles other α_2 agonists, such as clonidine, with characteristic symptoms including miosis, apnea, bradycardia, hypothermia, dry mouth, and coma.¹³ Co-abuse of xylazine and fentanyl can manifest clinically with symptoms including hypotension, tachycardia, arrhythmias, and the development of severe necrotic skin ulcers.²⁶

Xylazine is a central nervous system depressant that induces drowsiness, amnesia, and profound reductions in breathing, heart rate, and blood pressure, potentially reaching dangerously low levels. When administered in high doses or in combination with other central nervous system depressants, xylazine can lead to loss of physical sensation, loss of consciousness, and potentiation of the effects of other drugs, complicating the presentation and treatment of overdose cases.²⁵

DIAGNOSTIC TOOLS AND LABORATORY FINDINGS

The diagnosis of xylazine and fentanyl co-abuse can present challenges as routine toxicology screens do not detect xylazine. Additional analytical methods are necessary to identify the presence of xylazine in cases of illicit drug overdoses, especially when there are indications or symptoms suggestive of xylazine exposure.²⁷ In March 2023, BTNX, a prominent manufacturer of fentanyl test strips, announced the development and distribution of a new batch of xylazine test strips. However, these test strips are not currently available for commercial purchase.²³

MANAGEMENT STRATEGIES

Emergency management of xylazine and fentanyl overdose:

In cases of suspected xylazine and fentanyl overdose, the primary goals of the healthcare team are to ensure respiratory support and maintain stable blood pressure. Emergency care measures may involve endotracheal intubation, intravenous fluid resuscitation, administration of vasopressors, electrocardiogram monitoring, and regular monitoring of blood glucose and electrolyte levels.¹³

While naloxone is recommended as an opioid overdose reversal medication, its effectiveness in addressing the respiratory impact of xylazine is limited because xylazine is not an opioid. The increasing prevalence of xylazine in the illicit opioid supply raises concerns about the potential reduced effectiveness of naloxone in certain overdose cases.²⁰

Withdrawal management and long-term recovery

Withdrawal management and long-term recovery from xylazine and fentanyl overdose pose significant challenges. Xylazine withdrawal shares similarities with clonidine or dexmedetomidine "rebound," characterized by sympathetic overactivity such as hypertension, anxiety, and jitteriness. Despite negative laboratory tests, clinicians should remain vigilant and actively manage these symptoms. Long-term effects may include insomnia, anxiety, and dysphoria.²⁴

Management strategies for xylazine withdrawal may involve dexmedetomidine infusion, phenobarbital, and tizanidine, followed by a transition to clonidine. It is important to note the lack of reported cases on the management of chronic xylazine use and the absence of information regarding xylazine withdrawal management or ongoing treatment for individuals in recovery.²⁸

Psychosocial interventions and support services of xylazine and fentanyl overdose.

Psychosocial interventions and support services are valuable in the recovery of individuals who have undergone xylazine and fentanyl overdose. These interventions can be customized to meet individual needs and encompass various approaches such as addiction counselling, Cognitive Behavioral Therapy, Motivational Enhancement Therapy, Community Reinforcement Approach, contingency management, medication management, peer support, self-help, family therapy, and computer- or phone-based interventions. Such comprehensive psychosocial support plays a crucial role in the overall recovery process.²⁹

PREVENTION AND HARM REDUCTION

Public health initiatives and educational campaigns

Prevention and harm reduction play a crucial role in addressing the co-abuse of xylazine and fentanyl. Harm reduction is an effective approach that encompasses community-driven public health strategies, including prevention, risk reduction, and health promotion. It empowers individuals who use drugs and their families, allowing them to make informed decisions for healthy, self-directed, and purposeful lives.³⁰

Well-established harm reduction interventions include syringe service programs, overdose prevention sites, fentanyl testing, naloxone distribution and training, and provision of sterile injection or smoking equipment.³¹

Educational campaigns are valuable in preventing drug overdose fatalities. The Centers for Disease Control and Prevention (CDC) has developed four comprehensive education campaigns targeting young adults aged 18-34 years. These campaigns raise awareness about the prevalence and hazards of fentanyl, the risks and consequences associated with drug mixing, the life-saving potential of naloxone, and the significance of reducing stigma surrounding drug use to promote treatment and recovery. These initiatives aim to empower individuals with knowledge and resources to make informed decisions and ultimately reduce the devastating impact of drug overdoses.³²

Strategies for reducing Polydrug co-abuse incidents

Polydrug use involves the simultaneous use of illicit drugs and legal substances, increasing both acute and chronic risks. Interactions between substances can amplify dangers, such as combining cocaine and alcohol. Consequences of polydrug use include higher risks of fatal and non-fatal overdoses, accidents, liver damage, co-dependency, and compromised treatment outcomes. Strategies for reducing polydrug abuse incidents include non-substance-specific prevention approaches, identifying problematic polydrug use in treatment clients, and providing effective drug treatment.

Harm reduction measures, like addressing alcohol and drug misuse in festival and nightlife settings, and raising awareness about medicine misuse, can help mitigate harm. Overdose prevention, particularly for opioid users, involves educating about risks associated with combining opioids with other depressant substances like alcohol and benzodiazepines.³³

Importance of Polydrug Co-Abuse Awareness and Knowledge Dissemination in India

Addressing the urgent issue of xylazine and fentanyl co-abuse in India necessitates a focused approach on raising awareness and disseminating knowledge. By prioritizing education campaigns, research initiatives, and evidence-based strategies, we can effectively tackle the dangers of polydrug co-abuse. Increasing awareness among healthcare professionals, policymakers, and the general public is crucial for early identification, prevention, and appropriate interventions.

This review emphasizes the significance of comprehensive awareness efforts in creating a safer and healthier society in India. Through collective efforts, we can combat the complexities of polydrug co-abuse and pave the way for a brighter future.

Existing preventive measures for Polydrug Co-abuse in India

The Ministry of Social Justice and Empowerment in India launched the *Nasha Mukta Bharat Abhiyaan* (NMBA) in August 2020 to address drug abuse among youth in 272 vulnerable districts. The Abhiyaan focuses on involving stakeholders such as women, children,

educational institutions, and civil society organizations. 8,000 Master Volunteers have been trained to lead activities in these districts, reaching out to over 11.99+ Crore people through various on-ground activities.

Additionally, around 4,000+ Yuva Mandals, NYKS & NSS Volunteers, and Youth Clubs have been associated with the Abhiyaan.³⁴

CONCLUSION

The co-abuse of xylazine and fentanyl presents a significant global concern, with dangerous effects that demand immediate attention. Polydrug use is a complicated issue that demands further exploration to fully grasp its underlying causes and effects. The prevalence of this polydrug abuse across the world underscores the urgent need to raise awareness and enhance understanding regarding its repercussions. Specifically, in the context of India, where polydrug co-abuse is a growing issue, there is a pressing need to generate knowledge and develop targeted interventions. Future research could delve into the behavioural and neural mechanisms that drive polydrug use, with the aim of developing effective prevention and treatment approaches. Additionally, there is a need for more extensive research on the prevalence and patterns of polydrug use across different populations, including India. Such information could be instrumental in informing the development of targeted interventions aimed at mitigating the harm associated with polydrug use. By addressing the unique challenges posed by xylazine and fentanyl co-abuse, we can work towards mitigating its devastating consequences and safeguarding the well-being of individuals affected by this alarming trend.

ABBREVIATIONS

FDA	: Food and Drug Administration
NIDA	: National Institute on Drug Abuse
ODD	: Opioid Use Disorder
CDC	: Centers for Disease Control and Prevention
NMBA	: Nasha Mukta Bharat Abhiyaan
ATP	: Adenosine Triphosphate
Camp	: Cyclic Adenosine Monophosphate
CREB	: cAMP Response Element Binding Protein
BDNF	: Brain-Derived Neurotrophic Factor
PKA	: Protein Kinase A
PKC	: Protein Kinase C

CAS : Chemical Abstract Services
IUPAC : International Union of Pure and Applied Chemistry

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